

Engagement of citizens in co-designing citizen science studies in environmental epidemiology: Opportunities and challenges

David Kocman¹, Johanna Amelia Robinson^{1,2}, Rok Novak^{1,2}, Tjaša Kanduč¹, Miha Pratneker¹ and Jure Ftičar¹

¹*Jožef Stefan Institute, Department of Environmental Sciences, Ljubljana, SLOVENIA*

²*Jožef Stefan International Postgraduate School, Ljubljana, SLOVENIA*

Author email: david.kocman@ijs.si

Citizen Science (CS) is a rapidly growing field of research, increasingly used, among others, in various aspects of environmental health monitoring and health science, including environmental epidemiology. Its major advantage lies in the fact that CS facilitates inclusion of general public in scientific research processes. In recent years, there is a noticeable trend in CS projects - transition from more passive forms of participation, often limited to data collection, to active involvement of citizens in all project phases and research activities (co-created CS). This is largely supported by the rapid development of sensing and supporting information and communications technologies. While co-creation brings new opportunities, a number of challenges still exist and need to be considered when implementing respective CS activities. In this contribution, some of these opportunities and challenges will be discussed, both of technological and non-technological natures, based on hands-on experience in selected past and on-going CS projects. The general aspects discussed comprise, but are not limited to, the following: (i) user-centered design of tools and their fitness for purpose evaluation; (ii) societal vs. scientific relevance of CS activities; (iii) levels of collaboration between researchers and citizen scientists in data analyzing and knowledge generation; (iv) data governance and ownership, including intellectual property aspects; (v) management of volunteer motivations and expectations; (vi) educational value of CS when integrated in the school curriculum; and (vii) measuring the impact of citizen science including user-experience aspects.

KEYNOTE TALK